

DIGITAL MARKETING: CURRENT TRENDS IN INDIA
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Abstract:

*The rapidly emerging digitalization in economy is challenging the relevance of existing marketing practices and a radical design of the marketing curriculum consistent with the emerging student and **business needs of the 21st century** is required to remain relevant to our students and to the ultimate consumers of our output business, the curriculum of marketing must evolve with both the changing technological environment and the way marketing is perceived by its own academic architects after an overview of recent marketing trends his article describe the need for a fundamental change in the teaching of marketing in today's environment performs a curriculum audit of existing digital marketing initiatives and then details of a ideal curriculum reflective of marketing in a digital age and an approach to make it effective. The approach explored here provides other universities target to serve as one measure of progress towards a curriculum more in tune with the emerging digital environment.*

Keywords: *radical design, curriculum audit, marketing curriculum*

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Introduction:

In simplistic terms, digital marketing is the promotion of products or brands via one or more forms of electronic media. Digital marketing distinguish from traditional marketing in that it involves the use of channels and methods that enable an organization to analyze marketing campaigns and understand what is working and what isn't – typically in real time. Digital marketing or marketers monitor things like what is being viewed how often and for how long sales conversion what content works and doesn't work etc., while the internet is certainly, the channel most closely associated with the digital marketing. Others include wireless text, messaging, mobile instant messaging, mobile apps, Pod costs, electronic bill boards, digital television and radio channels etc.

Importance of Digital Marketing:

Digital media is applicable everywhere for which consumers have access to information any time and any place they want it gone are the days when the information people got about your products or services provided by you and consisted of only what you wanted them to know. Digital media is an ever growing source of entertainment news shopping and social interaction and customers or consumers are now unveiled not just what your company's claim about your product, but what the media, friends, relatives, peers, etc., are saying as well and they are more likely to believe them than you people want brands they can trust, companies that known them, communications that are personalized and relevant, and offers tailored to their needs and requirements as per society's concern.

Customer approach across all channels:

Digital marketing and its associated channels are significant but not to the very high extent it's not only enough to just know your customers you must know them anybody also so you can communicate with them where, when and how they are most recipient to your message. To do certain kind of activities like that you must need a consolidated feedback of customers preferences and expectations across all channels like web, social media, mobile, direct mail, point of sale etc.,. Marketers can use this information to create and anticipate consistent, coordinated customers' experience that will move customers along in buying cycle.

Challenges Facing in Digital Marketing

- Proliferation of digital channels
- Intensifying competition
- Exploding data volumes

Results:

As per the recent survey revealed that the uses of digital marketing and its standards is increasing extensively in the present era. Is most preferable market in India now-a-days? The digital marketing phenomenon is increasing rapidly not only in the urban vicinity of Indian territorial region, but also across the whole world. Henceforth, the digital marketing industry getting robust responses in Indian market.

Some numerical data is given below to support the statements:

Digital Advertising in India	
Year	Growth in %
2011	71
2012	64
2013	39
2014	27
2015	38
2016	45
2017	38
2018	34
2019	57
2020	62

Source: Group M Estimates

Table 1: Digital Advertising in India (Year viz. Year Growth)

Source: Group M Estimates

Digital Marketing-Connecting People:

Interpretation: India is connected through digital marketing results into connecting to each other in different ways. It is most effective worth project in India in present business scenario. Some of the medias are ppc, sms, mobile, augmented reality, seo, smo, email.,etc.,

Table 2: International View in Digital Marketing

Time Spent per Adult User per Day with Digital Media in INDIA 2013-2020				
Hours Per Day – Various Devices				
Year	Mobile	Desktop/Laptop	Other Connected Devices	Total
2013	0.3	2.2	0.2	2.7
2014	0.3	2.3	0.3	2.9
2015	0.4	2.4	0.4	3.2
2016	0.8	2.6	0.3	3.7
2017	1.6	2.5	0.3	4.4
2018	2.3	2.3	0.3	4.9
2019	2.6	2.4	0.3	5.3
2020	2.8	2.4	0.4	5.6

Graphical Interpretation

Interpretation:

The time spend per adult user with digital media, INDIA, 2013-2020 tears are as follows. On the x-axis it is taken as hours per day. On y-axis years are taken. Usage of mobile internet is more increasing now a day's Desktop usage seems constant from 2013 to 2020. Other connected devices are only 0.3% -0.4% only.

Conclusion:

Consumers use multiple digital channels and many devices that use different protocols, specifications and interfaces and they interact with those devices in different phases and for different purposes. Digital channels are relatively cheap, compared with traditional media, making them within each of practically every business of every size.

Suggestions:

Following are the three keys to get the success in the digital marketing area.

- Manage effective customer's relationships across a variety of channels both digital and traditional.
- Respond to and initiate dynamic customer interactions.
- Values can be derived from big data to make better decisions faster.

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